

COMPATIBILITY AND DURABILITY IN GLASS / PHENOLIC LAMINATING SYSTEMS.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of a wide-ranging study of commercially-available glass mats, including both square-weave woven roving (WR) and chopped-strand (CS) types, as reinforcements in cold-cure phenolic resins from two manufacturers. Laminates were manufactured by two routes: hand layup and resin-transfer moulding (RTM), using appropriate resin grades. In an initial sorting exercise, systems were evaluated by measurement of tensile properties, and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) by the short-beam bend test. Considerable variations in fibre / resin compatibility were found. On a basis of this work, systems were selected for the evaluation of their long-term stress-rupture characteristics under tensile load in air, and in water over a range of temperatures. Results are reported for tests of duration up to two and a half years on one such system. The WR mat which rated highest for compatibility was assessed in combination with the two preferred grades of resin, and processing route was found to have no clearcut effect on durability in air at room temperature. WR laminates produced by RTM were used to study the effect of water temperature on the stress-rupture life of immersed samples. As expected, higher temperatures produced shorter lives. The possibility of predicting service life from such tests by use of a time / temperature shift factor is discussed.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Polymer; Phenolic resin; Testing/Evaluation; Durability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Each new disaster where multiple deaths result from fire in confined spaces, reinforces the case for widespread substitution of common plastics by safer materials. The U.S. Federal Aviation Administration has recognised the urgency of this cause by introducing, in 1988, more stringent flammability regulations for materials in aircraft. Phenolics have among the best fire / smoke / toxicity (F/S/T) performance balances of all commercial resins, so that there is an upsurge of interest in these materials (1).

Composites with phenolic matrices cured under pressure at high temperatures were the first industrial polymers, but the cold-cure systems which are the subject of this paper are of relatively recent origin (2). They are phenolic resols, normally supplied in aqueous solution, which may be cured at ambient

pressure and temperature by the addition of an acid catalyst. Thus, they are suitable for the manufacture of large structures by hand layup, RTM, filament winding, etc (3), and are directly competitive with polyester and some epoxy systems.

By comparison with these well-established matrix materials, phenolics have the disadvantage that some commercially-available glass reinforcements, being formulated for compatibility with traditional matrices, are difficult to wet out, or act to inhibit the cure process, presenting problems in manufacture. There is also a lack of information concerning their long-term durability under stress, in aggressive environments such as water.

The authors have previously addressed the problem of compatibility for a single phenolic resin with commercial chopped-strand (CS) mats (4), and studied incompatibility at different stages of manufacture (5). The present paper reports a much wider survey of commercial resin / fibre combinations, and gives the results of durability tests on one selected system.

2. MATERIALS, SAMPLES AND TESTING

2.1 Materials All resins and reinforcements used were current industrial products. However, to remove any commercial implications from this work, reinforcements are identified by the symbols listed below, which are consistent with our earlier publications (4,5).

Chopped-strand mats of superficial weight 0.45kg/sq.m comprised two emulsion-bound (E1 and E2) and four powder-bound (P1 - P4). Three square-weave WR mats of superficial weight 0.78kg/sq.m were identified as W1 - W3. Resins were supplied by two manufacturers, identified as B and C, who each provided separate grades for hand layup (B1 and C1) and for RTM (B2 and C2).

2.2 Preparation of laminates Laminates 350 mm square, containing four layers of reinforcement, and with an overall thickness of 3mm, were produced by two routes. Hand layup was performed on a glass plate with Melinex lining. On completion a second lined plate was put on top, and the sandwich pressed down to stops in a clamping frame to give a board of uniform thickness. Catalyst content and cure time (24 hours at ambient temperature) were as recommended by the resin manufacturers. For RTM, a "Hypaject" moulding machine, made by Plastech TT, of Tavistock, U.K., was used. A weighed preform was clamped in a GRP mould, previously treated with release agent, and heated to 40C by built-in electrical heaters. Weighed quantities of resin and catalyst were pre-mixed in a vessel before being drawn into the moulding machine, and immediately injected into the mould by way of a centrally-placed gate. The mould temperature was then raised to 60C, and the laminate demoulded after two hours.

Some fibre / resin combinations failed to produce satisfactory laminates by either route, since the resin did not cure completely. In the remainder, for both manufacturing routes, careful preparation including control of thickness resulted in highly consistent fibre volume fractions of 0.25 +/- 0.02 for CS and 0.45 +/- 0.02 for WR reinforcements, as confirmed by burnoff tests.

2.3 Testpieces and short-term test methods Tensile testpieces were prepared by cutting strips of 40mm width with a diamond saw, and using a router to machine dumbbells with a 25mm parallel portion, 75mm long. The shoulder width was 35mm and the fillet radius 75mm. Identical testpieces were used for the stress-rupture tests. Samples for the short-beam bend test

were cut to 30mm long by 10mm wide. For glass content measurement, samples 50mm square were used.

Tensile tests were performed at a constant crosshead speed of 5mm per minute, with an optical extensometer for strain measurements based on a 50mm gauge length. At least five replicate tests were performed in each case. Parameters measured were tensile strength, initial tangent modulus and elongation at fracture, as per BS2782. For the short-beam test, three-point loading was used on a span of 15mm at a crosshead speed of 1mm per minute. The span to depth ratio was 5 to 1, as required by ASTM D2344. The criterion of failure was the first significant drop in the load / displacement record, which corresponded to the formation of an interlaminar crack near the sample mid-plane. The ILSS was calculated from the simple formula:

$$ILSS = 3P'/4wt$$

where P' is the failure load, w and t are the sample width and thickness. Between ten and fifteen samples from each laminate were tested.

2.4 Stress-rupture tests Stress-rupture tests were performed under tensile load imposed by weights acting through a first-order lever, maximum load capacity being 20kN. Load was transferred to the sample in a controlled manner by means of a screw jack. Samples to be tested in water were installed in the rig and soaked for 24 hours at the appropriate temperature before loading. Temperature control was by laboratory water-bath thermostat, to +/- 2C. The criterion of failure was complete separation of the sample. Times to failure were recorded by automatic timers for tests lasting up to ten days, and thereafter by regular inspection.

Since the testpieces were all of the same dimensions, it was possible to use the mean breaking load (MBL) of dry material from the tensile tests as a reference load for the stress-rupture tests. Samples were tested in groups of three or more under load at the following percentages of MBL: 80, 70, 60, 50, 40, 30 %MBL.

3 STATIC TESTS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Presentation of results Each test in turn was taken as a basis of comparison between the various combinations of resin and reinforcement, and Tables 1 to 4 show mean values, with standard deviation in brackets, for the respective properties: tensile strength, Young's modulus, failure strain and ILSS. Analysis was performed as follows. For each property, results were separated into two populations: WR and CS. Within these populations, each resin/reinforcement combination was treated as a separate class, and a one-way analysis of variance performed to establish whether variations between classes were significant, compared to variations within classes, at the 1% level of significance as measured by Snedecor's F-test. For failure strain, Table 3, the CS population showed no significant variation between classes. Thus the overall mean failure strain: 1.99% (s.d. 0.27%) may be taken as a representative value.

Where significant differences between classes were established, follow-up statistical tests were performed (see below). As a result, we have identified the three highest ranking classes in each population by stars in the accompanying Tables, and the three lowest by black marks.

3.2 Discussion The statistical follow-up test applied was to list the class means in rank order, and compare the observed differences between adjacent means with the calculated "least significant difference" (LSD) (6). Thus the population could be divided into groups, separated by differences significant at the 1% level. This procedure was successful for ILSS which,

as expected, was the most sensitive indicator of compatibility. CS laminates fell into three groups, with ILSS in the ranges 0-6, 7-14, and 15-20MPa. Two thirds of the population were in the middle group, with three in each of the extreme groups, as indicated in Table 4. For WR laminates also, three groups were found, with ranges 0-8, 12-18 and 21-30MPa. The distribution was entirely different, however, with only one in the lowest category, four in the middle and the majority, seven, in the top group.

These differences in class distribution, and more particularly in magnitude of ILSS, between the two populations, raise the question as to what is being measured by the short-beam bend test. It is difficult to see at first sight why the ILSS of WR laminates should be consistently higher than for CS, when the same resins and in some cases the same glasses are involved. By contrast it is easy to understand why, with samples of identical size, the failure load of a laminate under three-point bend with displacement control, should be higher for WR than for CS. The effective modulus of WR is higher than for CS, and the fibre volume fraction is appreciably higher, so that the bending stiffness of the beam will be greater. Since neither of these factors enters into the standard equation for calculation of ILSS, the precise meaning of these test results needs to be further investigated.

The above analysis was less successful for modulus and tensile strength measurements, and for failure strain of WR samples, because all values grouped together. Although a significant effect of class is observed, by comparison with the overall scatter, it is not possible to distinguish clearly between adjacent pairs of classes. Thus our identification of the top and bottom three classes in each population, though arbitrary, is not unreasonable.

It is impossible to draw unequivocal conclusions from these comparisons, since there are conflicting indications. The following remarks may be made. Reinforcements E1 and W3 and resin C1 show a preponderance of "worst" assessments and a dearth of "bests". E1 failed to produce satisfactory laminates with two of the resins. The high value of failure strain for systems B2/W3 and C1/W1 are uncertain as indicators of quality, especially as they are associated with low strength and modulus values. Our attempt to be objective and quantitative in our assessment is undermined by the fact that we were obliged to reject resin C2, despite its high scores, because it was difficult to work with, causing problems of demoulding.

Our final selection was based mainly on ILSS, for the reasons stated above, and resins B1, B2 were used in conjunction with reinforcements P1, W1 to manufacture laminates for stress-rupture testing.

4. STRESS-RUPTURE TESTS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Results reported here are for laminates of woven roving W1 produced by hand layup with resin B1, and by RTM with resin B2. It is clear from Table 1 that there is little difference in short-term strength between these two systems, their respective mean strengths being 249 +/- 36MPa and 268 +/- 54MPa, limits being set at two standard deviations about the mean.

4.1 Behaviour in air Time-dependent behaviour of the two systems under static load in air is compared in Figure 1, where time to failure (t_{tf}) is plotted logarithmically against applied load, expressed as a percentage of the mean breaking load in a tensile test (%MBL). Experimental points show both completed tests and runouts, with durations up to three years. Linear regression plots are presented for completed tests only. Considering the quantity of available data and its variability, it would not be justifiable

to distinguish between these two populations, and we can conclude that, as for short-term strength, the manufacturing route has no significant effect on stress-rupture behaviour in air at room temperature.

For purposes of structural design, an important requirement is for accelerated tests which give a reliable prediction of long-term behaviour under service conditions. The tests reported in Figure 1 attempt to meet this need by using high levels of stress. Figure 1 suggests that, at worst, there is a decrease in allowable stress of around 6% of the short-term strength per decade of test life. However, tests of nearly three years duration were required to produce this information.

4.2 Behaviour in water To investigate the effect of an aggressive environment on the long-term behaviour of these laminates, and to obtain results capable of extrapolation, from tests of only a few months duration, samples were tested in water at elevated temperatures. At the same time, to check the validity of the extrapolation, tests were initiated at 20C, and allowed to run for up to three years. Results are presented in Figure 2 for all temperatures investigated except 70C, at which a limited number of tests were performed. Regression lines are plotted in Figure 2 for the other three high temperatures. Coefficients of correlation are in all cases above 90%, and the lines show relatively small differences in slope.

The consistency in these curves suggests that similar failure mechanisms are operating at the relevant temperatures, so that it would be reasonable to attempt an extrapolation based on the time-temperature superposition principle, as suggested by the work of Zhurkov (7). Accordingly, we have taken 60C as a reference temperature, and, selecting a constant value of load (50%MBL), determined the logarithmic shift factors $a(T)$ required to bring the curve for temperature T into coincidence with the reference curve. Enough tests were conducted at 70C and 50%MBL to determine a mean life under these conditions, of value: $\text{Log}(t_{tf}(\text{sec})) = 4.42$, so that a shift factor was determined for this temperature also.

It is an assumption of this approach that the variation of shift factor with temperature follows an Arrhenius equation with a constant activation energy. Thus in Figure 3 experimental values of $\log a(T)$ are plotted against reciprocal of the absolute temperature ($1/T$). For 60C and above, the points fall on a straight line, with correlation coefficient of 99%, appearing to confirm that a consistent mechanism is operating under these conditions. For prediction purposes, this line would be extrapolated to determine the shift factor at some lower temperature, and thereby, the stress-rupture curve at that temperature. The result of this extrapolation, to a temperature of 20C, is shown by the square symbol in Figure 3. The predicted stress-rupture curve for 20C is shown in Figure 2 as the dashed line. Comparison with the experimental points for 20C shows that the extrapolation gives an over-optimistic assessment of the laminate performance.

The experimental regression line for 20C, omitted from Figure 2 in the interests of clarity, is closely parallel to the other curves, but is much closer to the reference curve at 60C, requiring a logarithmic shift factor of only -0.86 instead of the predicted -1.47. See Figure 3.

The discrepancy between observed and predicted values of stress-rupture life suggests that there is a change of deterioration mechanism between 60C and 20C which promotes earlier failure. The nature of this change is not readily apparent. Work is continuing in an attempt to confirm or deny its existence.

5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Careful selection among available phenolic resins and glass reinforcements can yield great improvements in workability, and mechanical properties of the resulting laminate.

5.2 For a selected phenolic / woven-roving system, laminates of identical specification manufactured by hand layup and RTM show similar mechanical properties and stress-rupture behaviour in air.

5.3 Under tensile stress in air at room temperature, a phenolic / woven-roving laminate may fail by stress-rupture. Allowable stress decreases by 6% of the dry tensile strength for each tenfold increase in test life.

5.4 Under stress-rupture in water, failure stress for the above laminate decreases by 11% of the dry tensile strength for each tenfold increase in test life.

5.5 The slope of the stress-rupture curve is independent of water temperature in the range 20 - 90C, though the life at a fixed stress level is reduced as temperature rises.

5.6 When stress-rupture tests are performed at elevated temperatures, the life at room temperature predicted by time-temperature superposition is greater than that found by experiment. That is to say, the predictions are optimistic.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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TABLE 1
Commercial glass/phenolic composites compared on a basis of:
Mean Tensile Strength (sd) MPa

Resin type: Moulding:	B1		B2		C1		C2	
	Hand		RTM		Hand		RTM	
Emulsion bound CSM								
E1	97	(16)●	****		67	(5)●	***	
E2	108	(7)						
Powder bound CSM								
P1	123	(6)	114	(12)	104	(7)	132	(17)
P2	102	(10)	130	(8)	91	(5)●	139	(14)*
P3	117	(14)						
P4	119	(8)	143	(14)*			143	(9)*
Woven roving mat								
W1	241	(22)	260	(19)	244	(30)	259	(41)
W2	273	(23)*	312	(33)*	267	(28)	281	(42)*
W3	225	(54)●	232	(14)●	241	(25)●	263	(2)

TABLE 2.
Commercial glass/phenolic composites compared on a basis of:
Mean Young's Modulus (sd) GPa

Resin type: Moulding:	B1		B2		C1		C2	
	Hand		RTM		Hand		RTM	
Emulsion bound CSM								
E1	6.18	(0.6)	***		5.54	(0.9)●	***	
E2	6.22	(1.0)						
Powder bound CSM								
P1	7.97	(0.6)*	6.10	(0.7)	5.55	(0.4)●	7.73	(0.9)*
P2	6.36	(0.8)	7.18	(0.3)*	5.45	(0.5)●	6.64	(0.9)
P3	5.78	(0.8)						
P4	6.16	(0.6)	6.13	(0.7)			6.73	(0.8)
Woven roving mat								
W1	17.26	(1.6)	17.60	(1.3)*	18.30	(1.4)*	18.27	(1.2)*
W2	17.16	(0.6)	14.45	(1.5)	18.03	(0.9)	16.12	(1.3)
W3	15.77	(0.6)	12.47	(0.3)●	12.47	(3.0)●	10.84	(1.9)●

***** Did not cure

TABLE 3
Commercial glass/phenolic composites compared on a basis of:
Mean failure strain (sd) %

Resin type: Moulding:	B1 Hand	B2 RTM	C1 Hand	C2 RTM
Emulsion bound CSM				
E1	1.83 (0.4)	****	1.97 (0.3)	****
E2	1.89 (0.4)			
Powder bound CSM				
P1	1.52 (0.1)	1.08 (0.7)	1.98 (0.2)	1.78 (0.4)
P2	1.59 (0.2)	2.02 (0.3)	2.12 (0.4)	2.19 (0.2)
P3	2.10 (0.3)			
P4	2.44 (0.2)	2.41 (0.)		2.22 (0.2)
Woven roving mat				
W1	1.30 (0.1)●	1.47 (0.3)●	2.36 (0.5)*	
W2	1.37 (0.1)●	2.50 (0.4)*	1.54 (0.3)	
W3	1.82 (0.0)	2.28 (0.3)*	2.26 (0.3)	

TABLE 4.
Commercial glass/phenolic composites compared on a basis of:
Mean I.L.S.S. (sd) MPa

Resin type: Moulding:	B1 Hand	B2 RTM	C1 Hand	C2 RTM
Emulsion bound CSM				
E1	8.47 (0.61)	****	3.79 (0.26)●	****
E2	7.40 (1.22)		5.93 (0.81)●	
Powder bound CSM				
P1	15.84 (0.53)*	19.43 (0.37)*	9.33 (0.52)	18.57 (1.52)*
P2	12.71 (1.30)	10.93 (0.49)	4.49 (0.54)●	9.42 (1.03)
P3	13.61 (1.12)		8.27 (0.43)	
P4	10.21 (1.09)	10.36 (0.45)	8.94 (2.16)	12.26 (0.53)
Woven roving mat				
W1	29.12 (1.42)*	28.04 (1.46)*	17.85 (1.94)	23.41 (1.14)
W2	21.00 (0.55)	26.31 (3.57)*	21.45 (2.06)	24.75 (1.90)
W3	13.28 (2.44)●	15.17 (0.44)	7.75 (1.28)●	11.99 (1.23)●

**** Did not cure

Figure 1. Stress-rupture plots for phenolic / woven-roving laminates in air at room temperature.
 HL = hand layup, resin B1, reinforcement W1.
 RTM = resin transfer moulding, resin B2, reinforcement W1.

Figure 2. Stress-rupture plots for phenolic / woven-roving laminates in water at indicated temperatures. Resin B2, reinforcement W1. Dashed line is predicted plot for 20C, by extrapolation from high-temperature tests using time-temperature superposition.

Figure 3. Shift factors for the superposition of stress-rupture plots in Figure 2, with 60C as the reference temperature. For 20C, extrapolated and observed values are shown.